

Annexe II - Codes source CachePagOS

Version Dev-C++ / RedPanda C++ - MinGW-w64 GCC 11.5.0 64-bit

Prototype Windows-first : runtime DLL, test fonctionnel et benchmark de prefetch

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Objet de cette annexe

Cette annexe regroupe les sources C++ utilisés pour la version prototype CachePagOS testée sous Windows avec Dev-C++ / RedPanda C++ et MinGW-w64 GCC 11.5.0 64-bit. **Elle accompagne l'annexe de tests techniques et sert de référence de reproduction.**

Périmètre des sources listées

1. pagos_runtime.h - interface C exportée par la DLL CachePagOS.
2. pagos_runtime.cpp - implémentation runtime : mapping CPAGOS/GGUF, validation, pointeurs tenseurs, prefetch Windows et correction des tenseurs globaux.
3. test_pagos_runtime/main.cpp - test fonctionnel minimal de la DLL.
4. benchmark_pagos_prefetch/main.cpp - benchmark décisionnel de prefetch utilisé pour Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.
5. README_BUILD.txt - notes de compilation et règles RedPanda / MinGW.

Règles de compilation

Compilation DLL : g++ -std=c++17 -O2 -shared pagos_runtime.cpp -o pagos_runtime.dll -Wl,--out-implib,libpagos_runtime.a

Compilation EXE : g++ -std=c++17 -O2 main.cpp libpagos_runtime.a -o <programme>.exe

Règle importante : ne jamais ajouter pagos_runtime.cpp dans les projets EXE si ceux-ci lient déjà libpagos_runtime.a, sinon le linker signale des définitions multiples.

1. pagos_runtime.h

Header final v0.4, incluant PagosProfileStats, pagos_prefetch_profile et pagos_get_profile_stats.

Fichier source : [pagos_runtime_v0_4.h](#) - 101 lignes

```
0001 // pagos_runtime.h
0002 // CachePagOS runtime API v0.4
0003 // Dev-C++ / RedPanda C++ - MinGW-w64 GCC 11.5.0 64-bit
0004 #pragma once
0005
0006 #include <stdint.h>
0007
0008 #ifdef WIN32
0009 #ifdef PAGOS_RUNTIME_EXPORTS
0010 #define PAGOS_API __declspec(dllexport)
0011 #else
0012 #define PAGOS_API __declspec(dllimport)
0013 #endif
0014 #else
0015 #define PAGOS_API
0016 #endif
0017
0018 #ifdef __cplusplus
0019 extern "C" {
0020 #endif
0021     enum PagosResult {
0022         PAGOS_OK = 0,
0023         PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT = 1,
0024         PAGOS_ERR_OPEN_FILE = 2,
0025         PAGOS_ERR_MAP_FILE = 3,
0026         PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_CPAGOS = 4,
0027         PAGOS_ERR_GGUF_MISMATCH = 5,
0028         PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE = 6,
0029         PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL = 100
0030     };
0031
0032     enum PagosProfile {
0033         PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE = 0,
0034         PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED = 1,
0035         PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION = 2
0036     };
0037
0038     struct PagosProfileStats {
0039         uint32_t executed_pages;
0040         uint32_t skipped_pages;
0041         uint32_t active_tensors;
0042         uint32_t total_tensors;
0043         uint64_t active_bytes;
0044         double page_coverage;
0045     };
0046
0047     PAGOS_API int pagos_open(
0048         const char* gguf_path,
0049         const char* cpagos_path,
0050         void** out_handle
0051     );
0052
0053     PAGOS_API int pagos_close(
0054         void* handle
0055     );
0056
0057     PAGOS_API int pagos_get_page_count(
0058         void* handle,
0059         uint32_t* out_count
0060     );
0061
0062     PAGOS_API int pagos_get_tensor_count(
0063         void* handle,
0064         uint32_t* out_count
0065     );
0066
0067     PAGOS_API int pagos_get_bundle_count(
0068         void* handle,
0069         uint32_t* out_count
0070     );
0071
0072     PAGOS_API int pagos_select_profile(
```

```
0073         void* handle,
0074         int profile
0075     );
0076
0077     PAGOS_API int pagos_get_tensor_ptr(
0078         void* handle,
0079         uint32_t tensor_id,
0080         const void** out_ptr,
0081         uint64_t* out_size
0082     );
0083
0084     PAGOS_API int pagos_prefetch_profile(
0085         void* handle,
0086         int profile
0087     );
0088
0089     PAGOS_API int pagos_get_profile_stats(
0090         void* handle,
0091         int profile,
0092         PagosProfileStats* out_stats
0093     );
0094
0095     PAGOS_API const char* pagos_last_error(
0096         void* handle
0097     );
0098
0099 #ifdef __cplusplus
0100 }
0101 #endif
```

2. pagos_runtime.cpp

Implémentation finale v0.4 : mapping, hash GGUF, prefetch dynamique, statistiques de profil et inclusion des tenseurs globaux.

Fichier source : [pagos_runtime_v0_4.cpp](#) - 935 lignes

```
0001 // pagos_runtime.cpp
0002 // pagos_runtime.dll v0.2
0003 //
0004 // C++17 / MinGW-w64 / RedPanda compatible
0005 //
0006 // v0.2:
0007 // - maps .cpagos
0008 // - maps .gguf
0009 // - validates GGUF size/hash against CPAGOS header
0010 // - exposes tensor direct pointer
0011 // - adds pagos_prefetch_profile() using Windows PrefetchVirtualMemory
0012
0013 #define PAGOS_RUNTIME_EXPORTS
0014 #include "pagos_runtime.h"
0015
0016 #include <windows.h>
0017
0018 #include <cstdint>
0019 #include <cstring>
0020 #include <fstream>
0021 #include <sstream>
0022 #include <stdexcept>
0023 #include <string>
0024
0025 static constexpr uint64_t CPAGOS_MAGIC = 0x0053474150475043ULL;
0026 static constexpr uint32_t CPAGOS_VERSION = 0;
0027 static constexpr uint32_t CPAGOS_ALIGNMENT = 65536;
0028 static constexpr uint32_t CPAGOS_GLOBAL_PAGE_ID = 0xFFFFFFFFFu;
0029
0030 static std::string g_last_error;
0031
0032 enum CPagosSectionType : uint32_t {
0033     CPAGOS_SECTION_MODEL_INFO = 1,
0034     CPAGOS_SECTION_PAGE_TABLE = 2,
0035     CPAGOS_SECTION_TENSOR_TABLE = 3,
0036     CPAGOS_SECTION_BUNDLE_TABLE = 4,
0037     CPAGOS_SECTION_HINT_TABLE = 5,
0038     CPAGOS_SECTION_VALIDATION = 6,
0039     CPAGOS_SECTION_DEBUG_TEXT = 7
0040 };
0041
0042 enum CPagosRole : uint32_t {
0043     CPAGOS_ROLE_CORE = 0,
0044     CPAGOS_ROLE_REFINEMENT = 1,
0045     CPAGOS_ROLE_OPTIONAL = 2,
0046     CPAGOS_ROLE_GLOBAL = 3
0047 };
0048
0049 #pragma pack(push, 1)
0050
0051 struct CPagosHeader {
0052     uint64_t magic;
0053     uint32_t version;
0054     uint32_t flags;
0055
0056     uint64_t file_size;
0057     uint64_t section_table_offset;
0058     uint32_t section_count;
0059
0060     uint32_t page_count;
0061     uint32_t tensor_count;
0062     uint32_t bundle_count;
0063
0064     uint64_t gguf_file_size;
0065     uint64_t gguf_hash_low;
0066     uint64_t gguf_hash_high;
0067
0068     uint32_t alignment;
0069     uint8_t reserved[52];
0070 };
0071
0072 struct CPagosSectionEntry {
```

```

0073     uint32_t type;
0074     uint32_t flags;
0075     uint64_t offset;
0076     uint64_t size;
0077 };
0078
0079 struct CPagosPageEntry {
0080     uint32_t page_id;
0081     uint32_t layer_index;
0082     uint32_t role;
0083     uint32_t tensor_count;
0084
0085     uint32_t first_tensor_index;
0086     uint32_t execution_order;
0087
0088     float priority_score;
0089     float estimated_cost;
0090
0091     uint64_t gguf_offset_min;
0092     uint64_t gguf_offset_max;
0093     uint64_t bytes_estimated;
0094 };
0095
0096 struct CPagosTensorEntry {
0097     uint32_t tensor_id;
0098     uint32_t page_id;
0099     uint32_t layer_index;
0100     uint32_t ggml_type;
0101
0102     uint64_t name_hash;
0103     uint64_t gguf_offset;
0104     uint64_t bytes_estimated;
0105
0106     uint64_t dim0;
0107     uint64_t dim1;
0108     uint64_t dim2;
0109     uint64_t dim3;
0110 };
0111
0112 struct CPagosBundleEntry {
0113     uint32_t bundle_id;
0114     uint32_t first_page_id;
0115     uint32_t page_count;
0116     uint32_t flags;
0117
0118     uint64_t total_bytes_estimated;
0119 };
0120
0121 struct CPagosHintEntry {
0122     uint32_t target_type;
0123     uint32_t target_id;
0124     uint32_t hint_flags;
0125     uint32_t priority;
0126
0127     uint64_t offset;
0128     uint64_t size;
0129 };
0130
0131 #pragma pack(pop)
0132
0133 static_assert(sizeof(CPagosHeader) == 128, "CPagosHeader must be 128 bytes");
0134
0135 // =====
0136 // MAPPED FILE
0137 // =====
0138
0139 struct MappedFile {
0140     HANDLE file = INVALID_HANDLE_VALUE;
0141     HANDLE mapping = NULL;
0142     void* base = nullptr;
0143     uint64_t size = 0;
0144
0145     void close() {
0146         if (base) {
0147             UnmapViewOfFile(base);
0148             base = nullptr;
0149         }
0150
0151         if (mapping) {
0152             CloseHandle(mapping);
0153             mapping = NULL;
0154         }
0155     }

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0156         if (file != INVALID_HANDLE_VALUE) {
0157             CloseHandle(file);
0158             file = INVALID_HANDLE_VALUE;
0159         }
0160         size = 0;
0161     }
0162 };
0163 };
0164
0165 struct PagosRuntime {
0166     MappedFile cpagos;
0167     MappedFile gguf;
0168
0169     const CPagosHeader* header = nullptr;
0170     const CPagosSectionEntry* sections = nullptr;
0171
0172     const CPagosPageEntry* pages = nullptr;
0173     uint64_t page_count = 0;
0174
0175     const CPagosTensorEntry* tensors = nullptr;
0176     uint64_t tensor_count = 0;
0177
0178     const CPagosBundleEntry* bundles = nullptr;
0179     uint64_t bundle_count = 0;
0180
0181     const CPagosHintEntry* hints = nullptr;
0182     uint64_t hint_count = 0;
0183
0184     int selected_profile = PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION;
0185
0186     std::string last_error;
0187 };
0188
0189 // =====
0190 // WINDOWS / UTILS
0191 // =====
0192
0193 static std::string win_error_string() {
0194     DWORD err = GetLastError();
0195     if (err == 0) {
0196         return "no error";
0197     }
0198
0199     LPSTR buffer = nullptr;
0200
0201     DWORD size = FormatMessage(
0202         FORMAT_MESSAGE_ALLOCATE_BUFFER |
0203         FORMAT_MESSAGE_FROM_SYSTEM |
0204         FORMAT_MESSAGE_IGNORE_INSERTS,
0205         NULL,
0206         err,
0207         MAKELANGID(LANG_NEUTRAL, SUBLANG_DEFAULT),
0208         (LPSTR)&buffer,
0209         0,
0210         NULL
0211     );
0212
0213     std::string msg = size && buffer ? buffer : "unknown Windows error";
0214
0215     if (buffer) {
0216         LocalFree(buffer);
0217     }
0218
0219     return msg;
0220 }
0221
0222 static MappedFile map_file_readonly(const char* path) {
0223     MappedFile mf;
0224
0225     mf.file = CreateFileA(
0226         path,
0227         GENERIC_READ,
0228         FILE_SHARE_READ,
0229         NULL,
0230         OPEN_EXISTING,
0231         FILE_ATTRIBUTE_NORMAL | FILE_FLAG_RANDOM_ACCESS,
0232         NULL
0233     );
0234
0235     if (mf.file == INVALID_HANDLE_VALUE) {
0236         throw std::runtime_error("CreateFileA failed for file: " + std::string(path) + " / " + win_error_string());
0237     }
0238 }

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0239 LARGE_INTEGER li_size{};
0240 if (!GetFileSizeEx(mf.file, &li_size)) {
0241     mf.close();
0242     throw std::runtime_error("GetFileSizeEx failed for file: " + std::string(path) + " / " + win_error_string());
0243 }
0244
0245 if (li_size.QuadPart <= 0) {
0246     mf.close();
0247     throw std::runtime_error("file is empty: " + std::string(path));
0248 }
0249
0250 mf.size = static_cast<uint64_t>(li_size.QuadPart);
0251
0252 mf.mapping = CreateFileMappingA(
0253     mf.file,
0254     NULL,
0255     PAGE_READONLY,
0256     0,
0257     0,
0258     NULL
0259 );
0260
0261 if (!mf.mapping) {
0262     mf.close();
0263     throw std::runtime_error("CreateFileMappingA failed for file: " + std::string(path) + " / " + win_error_string());
0264 }
0265
0266 mf.base = MapViewOfFile(
0267     mf.mapping,
0268     FILE_MAP_READ,
0269     0,
0270     0,
0271     0
0272 );
0273
0274 if (!mf.base) {
0275     mf.close();
0276     throw std::runtime_error("MapViewOfFile failed for file: " + std::string(path) + " / " + win_error_string());
0277 }
0278
0279 return mf;
0280 }
0281
0282 static const char* ptr_at(const MappedFile& mf, uint64_t offset, uint64_t size) {
0283     if (offset > mf.size || size > mf.size || offset + size > mf.size) {
0284         throw std::runtime_error("mapped pointer outside file");
0285     }
0286
0287     return reinterpret_cast<const char*>(mf.base) + offset;
0288 }
0289
0290 template<typename T>
0291 static const T* table_at(
0292     const MappedFile& mf,
0293     uint64_t offset,
0294     uint64_t size,
0295     uint64_t& out_count
0296 ) {
0297     if (size % sizeof(T) != 0) {
0298         throw std::runtime_error("section size is not a multiple of entry size");
0299     }
0300
0301     out_count = size / sizeof(T);
0302     return reinterpret_cast<const T*>(ptr_at(mf, offset, size));
0303 }
0304
0305 static const CPagosSectionEntry* find_section(
0306     const CPagosSectionEntry* sections,
0307     uint32_t section_count,
0308     uint32_t type
0309 ) {
0310     for (uint32_t i = 0; i < section_count; ++i) {
0311         if (sections[i].type == type) {
0312             return &sections[i];
0313         }
0314     }
0315
0316     return nullptr;
0317 }
0318
0319 static void hash_file_128_cheap(
0320     const char* path,
0321     uint64_t& low,

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```

0322                                     uint64_t& high,
0323                                     uint64_t& file_size
0324                                     ) {
0325     std::ifstream f(path, std::ios::binary);
0326     if (!f) {
0327         throw std::runtime_error("cannot open file for hash: " + std::string(path));
0328     }
0329
0330     uint64_t h1 = 1469598103934665603ULL;
0331     uint64_t h2 = 1099511628211ULL;
0332
0333     char buffer[1 << 16];
0334     file_size = 0;
0335
0336     while (f) {
0337         f.read(buffer, sizeof(buffer));
0338         std::streamsize n = f.gcount();
0339
0340         if (n <= 0) {
0341             break;
0342         }
0343
0344         file_size += static_cast<uint64_t>(n);
0345
0346         for (std::streamsize i = 0; i < n; ++i) {
0347             uint8_t c = static_cast<uint8_t>(buffer[i]);
0348
0349             h1 ^= c;
0350             h1 *= 1099511628211ULL;
0351
0352             h2 += c + 0x9e3779b97f4a7c15ULL + (h2 << 6) + (h2 >> 2);
0353             h2 ^= (h2 << 13);
0354             h2 ^= (h2 >> 7);
0355             h2 ^= (h2 << 17);
0356         }
0357     }
0358
0359     low = h1;
0360     high = h2;
0361 }
0362
0363 static int set_error(PagosRuntime* rt, const std::string& msg, int code) {
0364     g_last_error = msg;
0365
0366     if (rt) {
0367         rt->last_error = msg;
0368     }
0369
0370     return code;
0371 }
0372
0373 static void validate_cpagos_header(PagosRuntime* rt) {
0374     const CPagosHeader* h = rt->header;
0375
0376     if (!h) {
0377         throw std::runtime_error("null cpagos header");
0378     }
0379
0380     if (h->magic != CPAGOS_MAGIC) {
0381         throw std::runtime_error("invalid CPAGOS magic");
0382     }
0383
0384     if (h->version != CPAGOS_VERSION) {
0385         throw std::runtime_error("unsupported CPAGOS version");
0386     }
0387
0388     if (h->file_size != rt->cpagos.size) {
0389         throw std::runtime_error("CPAGOS file size mismatch");
0390     }
0391
0392     if (h->section_table_offset != sizeof(CPagosHeader)) {
0393         throw std::runtime_error("invalid section table offset");
0394     }
0395
0396     if (h->section_count == 0 || h->section_count > 64) {
0397         throw std::runtime_error("invalid section count");
0398     }
0399
0400     if (h->alignment != CPAGOS_ALIGNMENT) {
0401         throw std::runtime_error("invalid CPAGOS alignment");
0402     }
0403 }
0404

```

```

0405 static void validate_gguf_match(PagosRuntime* rt, const char* gguf_path) {
0406     uint64_t hash_low = 0;
0407     uint64_t hash_high = 0;
0408     uint64_t size = 0;
0409     hash_file_128_cheap(gguf_path, hash_low, hash_high, size);
0410
0411     if (size != rt->header->gguf_file_size) {
0412         throw std::runtime_error("GGUF size mismatch");
0413     }
0414
0415     if (hash_low != rt->header->gguf_hash_low ||
0416         hash_high != rt->header->gguf_hash_high) {
0417         throw std::runtime_error("GGUF hash mismatch");
0418     }
0419
0420     if (rt->gguf.size != rt->header->gguf_file_size) {
0421         throw std::runtime_error("mapped GGUF size mismatch");
0422     }
0423 }
0424
0425 static uint32_t pagos_profile_to_max_role(int profile) {
0426     switch (profile) {
0427     case PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE:
0428         return CPAGOS_ROLE_CORE;
0429
0430     case PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED:
0431         return CPAGOS_ROLE_REFINEMENT;
0432
0433     case PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION:
0434         return CPAGOS_ROLE_OPTIONAL;
0435
0436     default:
0437         throw std::runtime_error("invalid profile");
0438     }
0439 }
0440
0441 struct PagosMemoryRangeEntry {
0442     PVOID VirtualAddress;
0443     SIZE_T NumberOfBytes;
0444 };
0445
0446 typedef BOOL (WINAPI *PagosPrefetchVirtualMemoryFn)(
0447     HANDLE hProcess,
0448     ULONG_PTR NumberOfEntries,
0449     PagosMemoryRangeEntry* VirtualAddresses,
0450     ULONG Flags
0451 );
0452
0453 static bool pagos_prefetch_range_windows(
0454     PagosRuntime* rt,
0455     uint64_t offset,
0456     uint64_t size
0457 ) {
0458     if (!rt || !rt->gguf.base || size == 0) {
0459         return false;
0460     }
0461
0462     if (offset >= rt->gguf.size) {
0463         return false;
0464     }
0465
0466     if (offset + size > rt->gguf.size) {
0467         size = rt->gguf.size - offset;
0468     }
0469
0470     HMODULE kernel32 = GetModuleHandleA("kernel32.dll");
0471     if (!kernel32) {
0472         return false;
0473     }
0474
0475     PagosPrefetchVirtualMemoryFn pPrefetchVirtualMemory =
0476     reinterpret_cast<PagosPrefetchVirtualMemoryFn>(
0477         GetProcAddress(kernel32, "PrefetchVirtualMemory")
0478     );
0479
0480     if (!pPrefetchVirtualMemory) {
0481         return false;
0482     }
0483
0484     PagosMemoryRangeEntry range{};
0485     range.VirtualAddress = reinterpret_cast<PVOID>(
0486         reinterpret_cast<char*>(rt->gguf.base) + offset
0487

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0488                                     );
0489     range.NumberOfBytes = static_cast<SIZE_T>(size);
0490
0491     BOOL ok = pPrefetchVirtualMemory(
0492                                     GetCurrentProcess(),
0493                                     1,
0494                                     &range,
0495                                     0
0496                                     );
0497
0498     return ok != FALSE;
0499 }
0500
0501 static bool pagos_tensor_is_global(const CPagosTensorEntry& t) {
0502     return t.page_id == CPAGOS_GLOBAL_PAGE_ID;
0503 }
0504
0505 // =====
0506 // EXPORTED C API
0507 // =====
0508
0509 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_open(
0510                                     const char* gguf_path,
0511                                     const char* cpagos_path,
0512                                     void** out_handle
0513                                     ) {
0514     if (!gguf_path || !cpagos_path || !out_handle) {
0515         g_last_error = "invalid argument in pagos_open";
0516         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0517     }
0518
0519     *out_handle = nullptr;
0520
0521     PagosRuntime* rt = new PagosRuntime();
0522
0523     try {
0524         rt->cpagos = map_file_readonly(cpagos_path);
0525         rt->gguf = map_file_readonly(gguf_path);
0526
0527         rt->header = reinterpret_cast<const CPagosHeader*>(
0528                                     ptr_at(rt->cpagos, 0, sizeof(CPagosHeader))
0529                                     );
0530
0531         validate_cpagos_header(rt);
0532
0533         rt->sections = reinterpret_cast<const CPagosSectionEntry*>(
0534                                     ptr_at(
0535                                     rt->cpagos,
0536                                     rt->header->
0537                                     >section_table_offset,
0538                                     sizeof(CPagosSectionEntry)
0539                                     rt->header->section_count *
0540                                     );
0541
0542         const CPagosSectionEntry* page_sec =
0543             find_section(rt->sections, rt->header->section_count, CPAGOS_SECTION_PAGE_TABLE);
0544
0545         const CPagosSectionEntry* tensor_sec =
0546             find_section(rt->sections, rt->header->section_count, CPAGOS_SECTION_TENSOR_TABLE);
0547
0548         const CPagosSectionEntry* bundle_sec =
0549             find_section(rt->sections, rt->header->section_count, CPAGOS_SECTION_BUNDLE_TABLE);
0550
0551         const CPagosSectionEntry* hint_sec =
0552             find_section(rt->sections, rt->header->section_count, CPAGOS_SECTION_HINT_TABLE);
0553
0554         if (!page_sec || !tensor_sec || !bundle_sec || !hint_sec) {
0555             throw std::runtime_error("missing required runtime section");
0556         }
0557
0558         rt->pages = table_at<CPagosPageEntry>(
0559                                     rt->cpagos,
0560                                     page_sec->offset,
0561                                     page_sec->size,
0562                                     rt->page_count
0563                                     );
0564
0565         rt->tensors = table_at<CPagosTensorEntry>(
0566                                     rt->cpagos,
0567                                     tensor_sec->offset,
0568                                     tensor_sec->size,

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```

0569                                     rt->tensor_count
0570                                     );
0571
0572     rt->bundles = table_at<CPagosBundleEntry>(
0573
0574                                     rt->cpagos,
0575                                     bundle_sec->offset,
0576                                     bundle_sec->size,
0577                                     rt->bundle_count
0578                                     );
0579
0580     rt->hints = table_at<CPagosHintEntry>(
0581
0582                                     rt->cpagos,
0583                                     hint_sec->offset,
0584                                     hint_sec->size,
0585                                     rt->hint_count
0586                                     );
0587
0588     if (rt->page_count != rt->header->page_count) {
0589         throw std::runtime_error("page table count mismatch");
0590     }
0591
0592     if (rt->tensor_count != rt->header->tensor_count) {
0593         throw std::runtime_error("tensor table count mismatch");
0594     }
0595
0596     if (rt->bundle_count != rt->header->bundle_count) {
0597         throw std::runtime_error("bundle table count mismatch");
0598     }
0599
0600     validate_gguf_match(rt, gguf_path);
0601
0602     rt->selected_profile = PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION;
0603     rt->last_error.clear();
0604     g_last_error.clear();
0605
0606     *out_handle = rt;
0607     return PAGOS_OK;
0608 } catch (const std::exception& e) {
0609     g_last_error = e.what();
0610
0611     if (rt) {
0612         rt->last_error = e.what();
0613         rt->cpagos.close();
0614         rt->gguf.close();
0615         delete rt;
0616     }
0617     return PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL;
0618 }
0619 }
0620
0621 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_close(void* handle) {
0622     if (!handle) {
0623         g_last_error = "invalid handle in pagos_close";
0624         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0625     }
0626
0627     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0628
0629     rt->cpagos.close();
0630     rt->gguf.close();
0631
0632     delete rt;
0633
0634     return PAGOS_OK;
0635 }
0636
0637 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_get_page_count(
0638     void* handle,
0639     uint32_t* out_count
0640 ) {
0641     if (!handle || !out_count) {
0642         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0643     }
0644
0645     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0646     *out_count = static_cast<uint32_t>(rt->page_count);
0647
0648     return PAGOS_OK;
0649 }
0650
0651 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_get_tensor_count(

```

```

0652                                     void* handle,
0653                                     uint32_t* out_count
0654                                     ) {
0655     if (!handle || !out_count) {
0656         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0657     }
0658     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0659     *out_count = static_cast<uint32_t>(rt->tensor_count);
0660
0661     return PAGOS_OK;
0662 }
0663
0664 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_get_bundle_count(
0665                                     void* handle,
0666                                     uint32_t* out_count
0667                                     ) {
0668     if (!handle || !out_count) {
0669         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0670     }
0671     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0672     *out_count = static_cast<uint32_t>(rt->bundle_count);
0673
0674     return PAGOS_OK;
0675 }
0676
0677 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_select_profile(
0678                                     void* handle,
0679                                     int profile
0680                                     ) {
0681     if (!handle) {
0682         g_last_error = "invalid handle in pagos_select_profile";
0683         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0684     }
0685     if (profile < PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE ||
0686         profile > PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION) {
0687         return set_error(
0688             reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle),
0689             "invalid profile in pagos_select_profile",
0690             PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT
0691         );
0692     }
0693     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0694     rt->selected_profile = profile;
0695
0696     return PAGOS_OK;
0697 }
0698
0699 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_get_tensor_ptr(
0700                                     void* handle,
0701                                     uint32_t tensor_id,
0702                                     const void** out_ptr,
0703                                     uint64_t* out_size
0704                                     ) {
0705     if (!handle || !out_ptr || !out_size) {
0706         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0707     }
0708     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0709     if (tensor_id >= rt->tensor_count) {
0710         return set_error(rt, "tensor_id out of range", PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE);
0711     }
0712     const CPagosTensorEntry& t = rt->tensors[tensor_id];
0713     if (t.gguf_offset + t.bytes_estimated > rt->gguf.size) {
0714         return set_error(rt, "tensor span outside GGUF mapping", PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE);
0715     }
0716     *out_ptr = reinterpret_cast<const char*>(rt->gguf.base) + t.gguf_offset;
0717     *out_size = t.bytes_estimated;
0718
0719     return PAGOS_OK;
0720 }
0721
0722 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_prefetch_profile(
0723                                     void* handle,
0724                                     int profile
0725                                     ) {
0726
0727
0728
0729
0730
0731
0732
0733
0734

```

```

0735 if (!handle) {
0736     g_last_error = "invalid handle in pagos_prefetch_profile";
0737     return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0738 }
0739
0740 if (profile < PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE ||
0741     profile > PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION) {
0742     return set_error(
0743         reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle),
0744         "invalid profile in pagos_prefetch_profile",
0745         PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT
0746     );
0747 }
0748
0749 PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0750
0751 try {
0752     uint32_t max_role = pagos_profile_to_max_role(profile);
0753
0754     uint32_t attempted_pages = 0;
0755     uint32_t succeeded_pages = 0;
0756     uint32_t skipped_pages = 0;
0757
0758     uint32_t attempted_globals = 0;
0759     uint32_t succeeded_globals = 0;
0760
0761     for (uint64_t i = 0; i < rt->page_count; ++i) {
0762         const CPagosPageEntry& page = rt->pages[i];
0763
0764         if (page.role > max_role) {
0765             skipped_pages++;
0766             continue;
0767         }
0768
0769         if (page.gguf_offset_max <= page.gguf_offset_min) {
0770             skipped_pages++;
0771             continue;
0772         }
0773
0774         uint64_t offset = page.gguf_offset_min;
0775         uint64_t size = page.gguf_offset_max - page.gguf_offset_min;
0776
0777         attempted_pages++;
0778
0779         if (pagos_prefetch_range_windows(rt, offset, size)) {
0780             succeeded_pages++;
0781         }
0782     }
0783
0784     // v0.4 correction:
0785     // Les tenseurs globaux hors pages doivent etre precharges dans tous les profils.
0786     for (uint64_t i = 0; i < rt->tensor_count; ++i) {
0787         const CPagosTensorEntry& t = rt->tensors[i];
0788
0789         if (!pagos_tensor_is_global(t)) {
0790             continue;
0791         }
0792
0793         if (t.bytes_estimated == 0) {
0794             continue;
0795         }
0796
0797         if (t.gguf_offset >= rt->gguf.size) {
0798             continue;
0799         }
0800
0801         uint64_t size = t.bytes_estimated;
0802
0803         if (t.gguf_offset + size > rt->gguf.size) {
0804             size = rt->gguf.size - t.gguf_offset;
0805         }
0806
0807         attempted_globals++;
0808
0809         if (pagos_prefetch_range_windows(rt, t.gguf_offset, size)) {
0810             succeeded_globals++;
0811         }
0812     }
0813
0814     std::ostringstream oss;
0815     oss << "prefetch profile=" << profile
0816         << " page_attempted=" << attempted_pages
0817         << " page_succeeded=" << succeeded_pages

```

```

0818         << " page_skipped=" << skipped_pages
0819         << " global_attempted=" << attempted_globals
0820         << " global_succeeded=" << succeeded_globals;
0821
0822         rt->last_error = oss.str();
0823         g_last_error = rt->last_error;
0824
0825         return PAGOS_OK;
0826     } catch (const std::exception& e) {
0827         return set_error(rt, e.what(), PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL);
0828     }
0829 }
0830
0831 extern "C" PAGOS_API int pagos_get_profile_stats(
0832
0833
0834
0835
0836
0837     if (!handle || !out_stats) {
0838         g_last_error = "invalid argument in pagos_get_profile_stats";
0839         return PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT;
0840     }
0841
0842     if (profile < PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE ||
0843         profile > PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION) {
0844         return set_error(
0845             reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle),
0846             "invalid profile in pagos_get_profile_stats",
0847             PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT
0848         );
0849     }
0850     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0851
0852     try {
0853         uint32_t max_role = pagos_profile_to_max_role(profile);
0854
0855         PagosProfileStats stats{};
0856         stats.total_tensors = static_cast<uint32_t>(rt->tensor_count);
0857
0858         for (uint64_t i = 0; i < rt->page_count; ++i) {
0859             const CPagosPageEntry& page = rt->pages[i];
0860
0861             if (page.role <= max_role) {
0862                 stats.executed_pages++;
0863                 stats.active_tensors += page.tensor_count;
0864                 stats.active_bytes += page.bytes_estimated;
0865             } else {
0866                 stats.skipped_pages++;
0867             }
0868         }
0869
0870         // v0.4 correction:
0871         // Ajouter les tenseurs globaux a tous les profils.
0872         uint32_t global_tensors = 0;
0873         uint64_t global_bytes = 0;
0874
0875         for (uint64_t i = 0; i < rt->tensor_count; ++i) {
0876             const CPagosTensorEntry& t = rt->tensors[i];
0877
0878             if (!pagos_tensor_is_global(t)) {
0879                 continue;
0880             }
0881
0882             global_tensors++;
0883             global_bytes += t.bytes_estimated;
0884         }
0885
0886         stats.active_tensors += global_tensors;
0887         stats.active_bytes += global_bytes;
0888
0889         if (rt->page_count > 0) {
0890             stats.page_coverage =
0891                 static_cast<double>(stats.executed_pages) /
0892                 static_cast<double>(rt->page_count);
0893         } else {
0894             stats.page_coverage = 0.0;
0895         }
0896
0897         *out_stats = stats;
0898     } catch (...) {
0899         return set_error(rt, "pagos_get_profile_stats failed",
0900             PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT);
0901     }
0902 }

```

```

0901     oss << "profile stats profile=" << profile
0902         << " executed_pages=" << stats.executed_pages
0903         << " skipped_pages=" << stats.skipped_pages
0904         << " active_tensors=" << stats.active_tensors
0905         << " total_tensors=" << stats.total_tensors
0906         << " active_bytes=" << stats.active_bytes
0907         << " global_tensors=" << global_tensors
0908         << " global_bytes=" << global_bytes
0909         << " page_coverage=" << stats.page_coverage;
0910
0911     rt->last_error = oss.str();
0912     g_last_error = rt->last_error;
0913
0914     return PAGOS_OK;
0915
0916 } catch (const std::exception& e) {
0917     return set_error(rt, e.what(), PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL);
0918 }
0919 }
0920
0921 extern "C" PAGOS_API const char* pagos_last_error(
0922
0923
0924     if (!handle) {
0925         return g_last_error.empty() ? "no global error" : g_last_error.c_str();
0926     }
0927
0928     PagosRuntime* rt = reinterpret_cast<PagosRuntime*>(handle);
0929
0930     if (!rt->last_error.empty()) {
0931         return rt->last_error.c_str();
0932     }
0933
0934     return g_last_error.empty() ? "no error" : g_last_error.c_str();
0935 }

```

```

void* handle
) {

```

3. test_pagos_runtime/main.cpp

Test fonctionnel minimal : ouverture runtime, stats de profils, prefetch, accès aux premiers tenseurs.

Fichier source : test_pagos_runtime_main.cpp - 128 lignes

```
0001 // main.cpp
0002 // test_pagos_runtime.exe
0003 // Test fonctionnel minimal de pagos_runtime.dll v0.4
0004
0005 #include <iostream>
0006 #include <iomanip>
0007 #include <cstdlib>
0008
0009 #include "pagos_runtime.h"
0010
0011 static const char* result_name(int r) {
0012     switch (r) {
0013         case PAGOS_OK: return "PAGOS_OK";
0014         case PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT: return "PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT";
0015         case PAGOS_ERR_OPEN_FILE: return "PAGOS_ERR_OPEN_FILE";
0016         case PAGOS_ERR_MAP_FILE: return "PAGOS_ERR_MAP_FILE";
0017         case PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_CPAGOS: return "PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_CPAGOS";
0018         case PAGOS_ERR_GGUF_MISMATCH: return "PAGOS_ERR_GGUF_MISMATCH";
0019         case PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE: return "PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE";
0020         case PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL: return "PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL";
0021         default: return "UNKNOWN";
0022     }
0023 }
0024
0025 static const char* profile_name(int p) {
0026     switch (p) {
0027         case PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE: return "CORE";
0028         case PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED: return "BALANCED";
0029         case PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION: return "PRECISION";
0030         default: return "UNKNOWN";
0031     }
0032 }
0033
0034 static void test_profile(void* handle, int profile) {
0035     PagosProfileStats stats;
0036
0037     int r = pagos_get_profile_stats(handle, profile, &stats);
0038
0039     if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0040         std::cout << "[TEST] stats failed for " << profile_name(profile)
0041                 << " / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0042         return;
0043     }
0044
0045     std::cout << "[TEST] profile " << profile_name(profile) << "\n";
0046     std::cout << "    executed_pages : " << stats.executed_pages << "\n";
0047     std::cout << "    skipped_pages : " << stats.skipped_pages << "\n";
0048     std::cout << "    active_tensors : " << stats.active_tensors
0049             << " / " << stats.total_tensors << "\n";
0050     std::cout << "    active_bytes : " << stats.active_bytes << "\n";
0051     std::cout << "    page_coverage : " << stats.page_coverage << "\n";
0052
0053     r = pagos_prefetch_profile(handle, profile);
0054
0055     if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0056         std::cout << "[TEST] prefetch failed for " << profile_name(profile)
0057                 << " / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0058     } else {
0059         std::cout << "[TEST] prefetch " << profile_name(profile)
0060                 << " : OK / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0061     }
0062 }
0063
0064 int main() {
0065     const char* gguf_path = "Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.gguf";
0066     const char* cpagos_path = "Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.cpagos";
0067
0068     void* handle = nullptr;
0069
0070     std::cout << "[TEST] opening runtime...\n";
0071
0072     int r = pagos_open(gguf_path, cpagos_path, &handle);
```

```

0073
0074 if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0075     std::cout << "[TEST] pagos_open failed: " << result_name(r) << "\n";
0076     std::cout << "[TEST] last error: " << pagos_last_error(nullptr) << "\n";
0077     return 1;
0078 }
0079
0080 std::cout << "[TEST] pagos_open: OK\n";
0081
0082 uint32_t page_count = 0;
0083 uint32_t tensor_count = 0;
0084 uint32_t bundle_count = 0;
0085
0086 pagos_get_page_count(handle, &page_count);
0087 pagos_get_tensor_count(handle, &tensor_count);
0088 pagos_get_bundle_count(handle, &bundle_count);
0089
0090 std::cout << "[TEST] pages : " << page_count << "\n";
0091 std::cout << "[TEST] tensors : " << tensor_count << "\n";
0092 std::cout << "[TEST] bundles : " << bundle_count << "\n";
0093
0094 std::cout << "[TEST] profile stats + prefetch\n";
0095 test_profile(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE);
0096 test_profile(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED);
0097 test_profile(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION);
0098
0099 for (uint32_t i = 0; i < tensor_count && i < 8; ++i) {
0100     const void* ptr = nullptr;
0101     uint64_t size = 0;
0102
0103     r = pagos_get_tensor_ptr(handle, i, &ptr, &size);
0104
0105     if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0106         std::cout << "[TEST] tensor " << i << " failed: " << result_name(r)
0107             << " / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0108         continue;
0109     }
0110
0111     std::cout << "[TEST] tensor " << std::setw(2) << i
0112         << " ptr=" << ptr
0113         << " size=" << size
0114         << "\n";
0115 }
0116
0117 pagos_close(handle);
0118
0119 std::cout << "[TEST] RESULT: PASS\n";
0120 return 0;
0121 }
0122
0123 #ifdef WIN32
0124 #include <windows.h>
0125 int WINAPI WinMain(HINSTANCE, HINSTANCE, LPSTR, int) {
0126     return main();
0127 }
0128 #endif

```

4. benchmark_pagos_prefetch/main.cpp

Benchmark décisionnel utilisé sur tiny et Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.

Fichier source : main.cpp - 289 lignes

```
0001 // main.cpp
0002 // benchmark_pagos_prefetch.exe
0003 //
0004 // Benchmark décisionnel CachePagOS.
0005 // Objectif : mesurer rapidement si pagos_prefetch_profile()
0006 // donne un effet observable sur l'accès aux tenseurs GGUF.
0007 //
0008 // Compilation :
0009 // g++ -std=c++17 -O2 main.cpp libpagos_runtime.a -o benchmark_pagos_prefetch.exe
0010 //
0011 // Fichiers nécessaires dans le dossier :
0012 // benchmark_pagos_prefetch.exe
0013 // pagos_runtime.dll
0014 // libpagos_runtime.a
0015 // pagos_runtime.h
0016 // llama-2-tiny-4kv-heads-4layers-random-Q2_K.gguf
0017 // llama-2-tiny-4layers.cpagos
0018
0019 #include <windows.h>
0020
0021 #include <cstdint>
0022 #include <iostream>
0023 #include <iomanip>
0024 #include <string>
0025
0026 #include "pagos_runtime.h"
0027
0028 static const char* result_name(int r) {
0029     switch (r) {
0030     case PAGOS_OK:
0031         return "PAGOS_OK";
0032     case PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT:
0033         return "PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_ARGUMENT";
0034     case PAGOS_ERR_OPEN_FILE:
0035         return "PAGOS_ERR_OPEN_FILE";
0036     case PAGOS_ERR_MAP_FILE:
0037         return "PAGOS_ERR_MAP_FILE";
0038     case PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_CPAGOS:
0039         return "PAGOS_ERR_INVALID_CPAGOS";
0040     case PAGOS_ERR_GGUF_MISMATCH:
0041         return "PAGOS_ERR_GGUF_MISMATCH";
0042     case PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE:
0043         return "PAGOS_ERR_OUT_OF_RANGE";
0044     case PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL:
0045         return "PAGOS_ERR_INTERNAL";
0046     default:
0047         return "UNKNOWN";
0048     }
0049 }
0050
0051 static const char* profile_name(int p) {
0052     switch (p) {
0053     case PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE:
0054         return "CORE";
0055     case PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED:
0056         return "BALANCED";
0057     case PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION:
0058         return "PRECISION";
0059     default:
0060         return "UNKNOWN";
0061     }
0062 }
0063
0064 static double now_ms() {
0065     static LARGE_INTEGER freq{};
0066     static bool initialized = false;
0067
0068     if (!initialized) {
0069         QueryPerformanceFrequency(&freq);
0070         initialized = true;
0071     }
0072 }
```

```

0073     LARGE_INTEGER counter{};
0074     QueryPerformanceCounter(&counter);
0075
0076     return (static_cast<double>(counter.QuadPart) * 1000.0) /
0077     static_cast<double>(freq.QuadPart);
0078 }
0079
0080 static uint64_t touch_memory(const void* ptr, uint64_t size) {
0081     if (!ptr || size == 0) {
0082         return 0;
0083     }
0084
0085     const volatile uint8_t* p = reinterpret_cast<const volatile uint8_t*>(ptr);
0086
0087     uint64_t sum = 0;
0088
0089     // Lecture par pas de 64 octets pour forcer un vrai parcours mémoire
0090     // sans coûter inutilement trop cher.
0091     for (uint64_t i = 0; i < size; i += 64) {
0092         sum += p[i];
0093     }
0094
0095     // Lire aussi le dernier octet si la taille n'est pas nulle.
0096     sum += p[size - 1];
0097
0098     return sum;
0099 }
0100
0101 static bool run_profile_benchmark(
0102                                     void* handle,
0103                                     int profile,
0104                                     uint32_t tensor_count
0105                                 ) {
0106     PagosProfileStats stats{};
0107
0108     int r = pagos_get_profile_stats(handle, profile, &stats);
0109
0110     if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0111         std::cout << "[BENCH] stats failed for " << profile_name(profile)
0112                 << " : " << result_name(r)
0113                 << " / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0114         return false;
0115     }
0116
0117     // Dans notre format actuel, les tenseurs de pages sont rangés par ordre de page,
0118     // puis les tenseurs globaux à la fin. Donc active_tensors correspond aux premiers
0119     // tenseurs actifs du profil.
0120     uint32_t active_tensors = stats.active_tensors;
0121
0122     if (active_tensors > tensor_count) {
0123         active_tensors = tensor_count;
0124     }
0125
0126     std::cout << "\n[BENCH] ===== PROFILE " << profile_name(profile) << " =====\n";
0127     std::cout << "[BENCH] executed_pages : " << stats.executed_pages << "\n";
0128     std::cout << "[BENCH] skipped_pages : " << stats.skipped_pages << "\n";
0129     std::cout << "[BENCH] active_tensors : " << stats.active_tensors
0130     << " / " << stats.total_tensors << "\n";
0131     std::cout << "[BENCH] active_bytes : " << stats.active_bytes << "\n";
0132     std::cout << "[BENCH] page_coverage : " << stats.page_coverage << "\n";
0133
0134     uint64_t checksum_without_prefetch = 0;
0135     uint64_t checksum_with_prefetch = 0;
0136
0137     // -----
0138     // Phase 1 : lecture sans prefetch explicite
0139     // -----
0140     double t0 = now_ms();
0141
0142     for (uint32_t i = 0; i < active_tensors; ++i) {
0143         const void* ptr = nullptr;
0144         uint64_t size = 0;
0145
0146         r = pagos_get_tensor_ptr(handle, i, &ptr, &size);
0147
0148         if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0149             std::cout << "[BENCH] tensor " << i << " failed before prefetch: "
0150                     << result_name(r) << " / "
0151                     << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0152             return false;
0153         }
0154
0155         checksum_without_prefetch += touch_memory(ptr, size);

```

```

0156 }
0157
0158 double t1 = now_ms();
0159
0160 // -----
0161 // Phase 2 : prefetch du profil
0162 // -----
0163 double p0 = now_ms();
0164
0165 r = pagos_prefetch_profile(handle, profile);
0166
0167 double p1 = now_ms();
0168
0169 if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0170     std::cout << "[BENCH] prefetch failed for " << profile_name(profile)
0171         << " : " << result_name(r)
0172         << " / " << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0173     return false;
0174 }
0175
0176 std::string prefetch_msg = pagos_last_error(handle);
0177
0178 // -----
0179 // Phase 3 : lecture après prefetch
0180 // -----
0181 double t2 = now_ms();
0182
0183 for (uint32_t i = 0; i < active_tensors; ++i) {
0184     const void* ptr = nullptr;
0185     uint64_t size = 0;
0186
0187     r = pagos_get_tensor_ptr(handle, i, &ptr, &size);
0188
0189     if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0190         std::cout << "[BENCH] tensor " << i << " failed after prefetch: "
0191             << result_name(r) << " / "
0192             << pagos_last_error(handle) << "\n";
0193         return false;
0194     }
0195
0196     checksum_with_prefetch += touch_memory(ptr, size);
0197 }
0198
0199 double t3 = now_ms();
0200
0201 double read_without_prefetch_ms = t1 - t0;
0202 double prefetch_ms = p1 - p0;
0203 double read_after_prefetch_ms = t3 - t2;
0204
0205 double delta = read_without_prefetch_ms - read_after_prefetch_ms;
0206
0207 std::cout << std::fixed << std::setprecision(4);
0208
0209 std::cout << "[BENCH] prefetch_msg      : " << prefetch_msg << "\n";
0210 std::cout << "[BENCH] read_without_prefetch: "
0211 << read_without_prefetch_ms << " ms\n";
0212 std::cout << "[BENCH] prefetch_call      : "
0213 << prefetch_ms << " ms\n";
0214 std::cout << "[BENCH] read_after_prefetch : "
0215 << read_after_prefetch_ms << " ms\n";
0216 std::cout << "[BENCH] delta_read        : "
0217 << delta << " ms\n";
0218
0219 if (read_without_prefetch_ms > 0.0) {
0220     double percent = (delta / read_without_prefetch_ms) * 100.0;
0221     std::cout << "[BENCH] delta_percent : "
0222     << percent << " %\n";
0223 }
0224
0225 std::cout << "[BENCH] checksum_without : "
0226 << checksum_without_prefetch << "\n";
0227 std::cout << "[BENCH] checksum_with : "
0228 << checksum_with_prefetch << "\n";
0229
0230 if (checksum_without_prefetch != checksum_with_prefetch) {
0231     std::cout << "[BENCH] WARNING: checksum differs. Memory read path may be inconsistent.\n";
0232 }
0233
0234 return true;
0235 }
0236
0237 int main() {
0238     const char* gguf_path =

```

```

0239 "llama-2-tiny-4kv-heads-4layers-random-Q2_K.gguf";
0240
0241 const char* cpagos_path =
0242 "llama-2-tiny-4layers.cpagos";
0243
0244 std::cout << "[BENCH] CachePagOS prefetch benchmark\n";
0245 std::cout << "[BENCH] GGUF : " << gguf_path << "\n";
0246 std::cout << "[BENCH] CPAGOS : " << cpagos_path << "\n";
0247
0248 void* handle = nullptr;
0249
0250 int r = pagos_open(gguf_path, cpagos_path, &handle);
0251
0252 if (r != PAGOS_OK) {
0253     std::cout << "[BENCH] pagos_open failed: "
0254     << result_name(r) << "\n";
0255     std::cout << "[BENCH] last error: "
0256     << pagos_last_error(nullptr) << "\n";
0257     return 1;
0258 }
0259
0260 uint32_t page_count = 0;
0261 uint32_t tensor_count = 0;
0262 uint32_t bundle_count = 0;
0263
0264 pagos_get_page_count(handle, &page_count);
0265 pagos_get_tensor_count(handle, &tensor_count);
0266 pagos_get_bundle_count(handle, &bundle_count);
0267
0268 std::cout << "[BENCH] pages : " << page_count << "\n";
0269 std::cout << "[BENCH] tensors : " << tensor_count << "\n";
0270 std::cout << "[BENCH] bundles : " << bundle_count << "\n";
0271
0272 bool ok = true;
0273
0274 ok = run_profile_benchmark(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_CORE, tensor_count) && ok;
0275 ok = run_profile_benchmark(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_BALANCED, tensor_count) && ok;
0276 ok = run_profile_benchmark(handle, PAGOS_PROFILE_PRECISION, tensor_count) && ok;
0277
0278 pagos_close(handle);
0279
0280 std::cout << "\n[BENCH] RESULT: " << (ok ? "PASS" : "FAIL") << "\n";
0281
0282 return ok ? 0 : 2;
0283 }
0284
0285 #ifdef WIN32
0286 int WINAPI WinMain(HINSTANCE, HINSTANCE, LPSTR, int) {
0287     return main();
0288 }
0289 #endif

```

5. README_BUILD.txt

Notes de compilation et organisation des projets Dev-C++ / RedPanda C++.

Fichier source : README_BUILD_CachePagOS_DevCpp_MinGW.txt - 48 lignes

```
0001 CachePagOS - Source appendix build notes
0002 Target environment: Dev-C++ / RedPanda C++ with MinGW-w64 GCC 11.5.0 64-bit.
0003
0004 1) DLL project: pagos_runtime
0005 Files:
0006 - pagos_runtime.cpp
0007 - pagos_runtime.h
0008 Project type:
0009 - DLL / shared library
0010 Compiler:
0011 - C++17
0012 Manual build command:
0013 g++ -std=c++17 -O2 -shared pagos_runtime.cpp -o pagos_runtime.dll -Wl,--out-implib,libpagos_runtime.a
0014
0015 Expected outputs:
0016 - pagos_runtime.dll
0017 - libpagos_runtime.a
0018
0019 2) Functional test project: test_pagos_runtime
0020 Files:
0021 - main.cpp
0022 - pagos_runtime.h
0023 Linker input:
0024 - libpagos_runtime.a
0025 Runtime files in the same folder as the exe:
0026 - pagos_runtime.dll
0027 - Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.gguf
0028 - Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.cpagos
0029 Manual build command:
0030 g++ -std=c++17 -O2 main.cpp libpagos_runtime.a -o test_pagos_runtime.exe
0031
0032 3) Benchmark project: benchmark_pagos_prefetch
0033 Files:
0034 - main.cpp
0035 - pagos_runtime.h
0036 Linker input:
0037 - libpagos_runtime.a
0038 Runtime files in the same folder as the exe:
0039 - pagos_runtime.dll
0040 - Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.gguf
0041 - Qwen3-0.6B-Q4_K_M.cpagos
0042 Manual build command:
0043 g++ -std=c++17 -O2 main.cpp libpagos_runtime.a -o benchmark_pagos_prefetch.exe
0044
0045 Important RedPanda/Dev-C++ rules:
0046 - Do not add pagos_runtime.cpp to the EXE projects if linking with libpagos_runtime.a.
0047 - Header files are included but not compiled alone.
0048 - If the project is accidentally built as GUI, either switch to Console Application or keep the WinMain wrapper.
```